

METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING “4K” EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES OF FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS IN DUAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article provides a detailed description of the organization of “4K” educational processes of future primary teachers in dual education.

In the world, research is being conducted in the following priority areas for the continuous development and variant modeling of the system of training future specialists: developing the professional and personal qualities of students based on integrated and differentiated education, introducing a credit-module system in the higher education process based on integrative and innovative technologies, developing socio-pedagogical technologies for training future teachers, ensuring the coherence and continuity of the system of training specialists with professionally oriented training models, improving the system of preparing students for professional activity, researching modern methods of assessing student knowledge in pedagogical education, and improving ways to use information models in the educational process. In particular, in the process of improving the organizational and pedagogical conditions for the training of future primary school teachers, developing their reflexive abilities in the process of finding solutions to practical and situational tasks, interdisciplinary integrative design in the development of general and specialized training modules, and the implementation of dual educational processes are of particular relevance.

According to the UNESCO International Standard Classification of Education, dual education involves the development and implementation of educational programs in harmony with practical activities in the production of the educational process, taking into account the vocational education systems of countries.

The dual model of training future teachers is an innovative training system built on the basis of the joint and cooperative activities of higher and public education, and is based on three methodological foundations: axiological (equal importance of humanistic and

technological values); ontological (competent approach); technological (organization of professional development processes, socio-professional relations).

The dual education system is used in a number of countries, in particular in Germany, Croatia, Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Denmark, Slovenia, Montenegro, Switzerland, the Netherlands and France, and in recent years in China and other Asian countries.

For young people in Germany, dual education is an excellent opportunity to achieve independence early and adapt to professional and labor activities. Unlike other countries, the main burden in the field of education in Germany falls on enterprises, which spend more than 40 billion euros annually on improving the professional qualifications of their employees. This amount is more than the state spends on financing universities. The state supports the training of specialists in enterprises by financing the system of vocational schools. Students attend educational institutions in the dual education system. The main task of the state is to coordinate and ensure the legislative framework. At the federal level, Germany has adopted the Vocational Education Act and the Code of Conduct, which regulates the relationship between students and companies and educational institutions. This law also determines which companies can participate in the program.

It is known that students have difficulty applying the knowledge they have acquired in the process of higher education in specific practical situations, and the skills they have are mainly reproducible. Based on this, organizing the educational process in pedagogical higher educational institutions of our Republic on the basis of the principle of dual education, facilitating the manifestation of the individuality of the individual through pedagogical support, and ensuring the variability of the content of education are important tasks, and extensive work is being carried out in this regard.

In our country, great attention is paid to raising the higher education system to a new qualitative level, ensuring the integration of education, science and production in the training of future specialists, and training innovative personnel who are competitive and creatively thinking based on advanced foreign experience. The new edition of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" for the first time established the legal status of dual education as a form of education.

R. Choriyev studied the issue of improving the methodology for training vocational education specialists for professional activity on the basis of the dual education system, while U. Turamurodov studied the problem of training psychologists in the conditions of dual education.

The process of training pedagogical personnel in the dual education system is carried out by organizing training in the "4 + 2" order. Starting from the 2022-2023 academic year, 5 pedagogical higher educational institutions in Tashkent and 17 in the regions have been permanently attached to schools. Students have been allowed to study in connection with schools from the 1st year. Increasing the effectiveness of this activity certainly requires reflexive knowledge and skills. This determines the need to introduce an innovative system for training future teachers in modern conditions and develop new models for training specialists with reflexive abilities. Improving the quality of teaching in the public education system is inextricably linked with the formation and development of the reflexive abilities of future teachers in pedagogical higher educational institutions. This indicates the need to

improve the pedagogical mechanisms for the formation of reflexive abilities in future primary school teachers, while expanding the didactic opportunities of dual education.

In the new edition of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education”, the concept of “dual education” is defined as follows: “Dual education is aimed at obtaining the necessary knowledge, qualifications and skills by students, the theoretical part of which is carried out on the basis of an educational organization, and the practical part is carried out at the student’s workplace” .

Also, in the official resolutions and decrees adopted by the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years, special attention is paid to the issue of the accelerated implementation of this educational model in the process of training pedagogical personnel. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 21, 2022 No. PQ-289 “On measures to improve the quality of pedagogical education and further develop the activities of higher educational institutions training pedagogical personnel” sets as a priority task “ensuring that weekly training sessions for students of the 2nd-4th year of full-time education in higher educational institutions training pedagogical personnel are conducted in the “4 + 2” format, including 4 days of classes in a higher educational institution and 2 days of practice in preschool and general secondary educational institutions”. The concept of “dual education” is used in both “narrow” and “broad” meanings. In a narrow sense, dual education is considered a new form of education, which determines the implementation of the theoretical part of the study in higher education institutions, and the practical aspects in the employer organization.

In essence, this is a special form of pedagogical practice carried out in a future educational organization within the framework of the educational program. The introduction of an educational organization into cooperation with an employer allows for the effective formation of both the professional competencies required by the higher education system and the student's readiness to perform labor tasks specified in the professional standard.

In a broad sense, dual education implies a specific model in which, taking into account the needs of the regions: the demand for pedagogical personnel is determined; their professional qualifications are monitored and assessed; conditions are created for professional growth and mastery of the profession; blended learning models for the training and improvement of pedagogical personnel are implemented; personnel training management is carried out through a public system.

Today, the dual education system is considered the most promising direction for the training of future teachers in accordance with professional standards. The dual education model is attracting increasing attention due to the following factors:

1. Curriculums are developed taking into account the proposals of employers, who form specific orders for educational organizations based on their needs for specialists. Employers are shown as interested participants in the educational process, actively participate in the selection of educational content, and in determining the processes of its implementation.

2. Students have the opportunity to undergo pedagogical practice in the workplace and gain practical experience specific to future teaching activities specified in the professional standard.

3. Special competencies that ensure the professional training of future teachers are mastered by students in continuing education institutions on the basis of dual education technologies.

4. The involvement of students in the real pedagogical process in continuing education institutions not only contributes to the acquisition of labor actions, necessary knowledge and skills, but also creates an opportunity for their personal and professional socialization, ensuring the formation of skills for working together.

5. Continuous pedagogical practice of student practitioners in educational institutions makes it possible to identify their strengths and weaknesses, and to find forms and methods for the effective mastery of professional activity by the student.

To better imagine the concept of dual education, it is necessary to note the following goals, objectives and principles of education.

Education goals specific to dual education:

- improving the vocational education system by forming an effective structure for the training of future teachers;
- introducing modern forms, methods and means of training into curricula and programs that determine the content of training future teachers;
- reforming the system of continuous vocational education;
- improving the professional standards of future teachers.

Education tasks specific to the dual education model:

- reorganizing the system of training future teachers based on labor market requirements;
- creating a cluster of vocational education organizations that meet the needs of social life and the labor market.
- radically changing and improving the curriculum and its structural foundations in a way that ensures professional mobility.
- creating material, technical and methodological support for the training of future teachers.

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